

ISic3571

Honours for Lapiron

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

tabula

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-10 - Jonathan Prag revised on basis of study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30595

Physical Description

Five joining fragments of a thin slab of cream marble with extensive blue veins. The right hand side of the text survives entire, with part of the top, right and bottom margins intact; the lower right corner is missing, but no text is there lost. On a conservative estimate, slightly more than half of the stone is missing on the left side.

Dimensions

Height 69.2 cm

Width 44 cm

Depth 1.6-2 cm

Layout

The right hand end of five lines of Latin text are preserved, with clear vacats above the first and below the final line. The text decreases in size from lines 1-4 (55-36 mm), and a slight gap precedes line 5, which is larger again (46 mm).

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 55 mm

Line 2: 45-48 mm

Line 3: 38-40 mm

Line 4: 36 mm

Line 5: 46 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. [---][La]pironi
2. [---][pr]aef(ecto) · fabr(um) · X
3. [---][flaminiAug]usti · Caesaris
4. [---][perpet]uo(vac.undefin)

5. [---][pecu]nia · publica

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

(In honour of) [---]Lapiron [---] praefectus fabrum 10 times [---] priest of Augustus Caesar, for life [---](set up at) public expense

Commentary

The name in line 1 can be restored on the basis of epigraphic and literary attestations from the second and first century BC of individuals at Halaesa with Greek names, called Diogenes Lapiron and Apollodorus Lapiron (see ISic1176 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1176>] , ISic0800 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0800>] , ISic1175 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1175>] , and Cicero, In Verrem 2.2.19 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi0474.phi005.perseus-lat1:2.2.19>] -28; Facella 2006: 230-232). This individual must be a Roman citizen, with the Greek name Lapiron forming the cognomen, and he is presumably a relative of those previously known. The suggested restorations of the other lines (especially line 4) allows for perhaps as many as 10 letters before Lapironi, but probably not more. This would be just sufficient for praenomen, short nomen, and filiation (or a slightly longer nomen if filiation were omitted). The fact that a member of one of the leading families of Halaesa in the Hellenistic/Republican period can be seen holding a position within the Roman state (praefectus fabrum) and (probably) being honoured in his hometown with the priesthood of Augustus for life is important evidence for continuity of the local elite in Halaesa through the troubled period of the civil wars and into the early Empire (there is no direct evidence for events in Halaesa during the civil wars).

In line 2, the restoration of praefectus fabrum is unproblematic. Iteration of the position 10 times (i.e. for ten years) is unusual, but not unparalleled (see e.g. AE 1959 no.284 [www.trismegistos.org/text/282233] , Saepinum, for 15 times). Several other individuals in Sicily (mostly early Empire) are attested as holding the office of praefectus fabrum, at Messina (ISic0265 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0265>] , lost), at Catania (ISic0307 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0307>]), and at Termini (ISic0094 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0094>] (lost) and ISic0098 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0098>]). Depending upon the available space to the left, a further office is likely to have been listed, and is more likely to have been one in imperial / military service, rather than municipal, given the sequence of posts, viz. praefectus fabrum in line 2 followed by a municipal priesthood in line 3 (the general of such military posts with municipal ones is

common). One likely such post would be that of *tribunus militum* (with or without the legion named), but *praefectus equitum* or *praefectus cohortis* are also attested.

In lines 3-4, *Augusti Caesaris* in the genitive is most frequently found in the context of a *flamen* (priest) *Augusti Caesaris*, which position is already attested at Halaesa on the Augustan-era coinage (RPC I, no.630-633, e.g. ANS 2015.20.550 [<http://numismatics.org/collection/2015.20.550>]). The word ending [-]VO in line four appears to stand alone at the centre of the line, and in context can most plausibly be restored as *perpetuo*, the position of *flamen perpetuus* (i.e. priest for life) being a relatively common honour in municipal careers. The layout implied by placing *perpetuo* at the centre of line 4 would mean that there was some space still before *flamini* on line 3 (since the text of line 3 runs right up to the margin on the right hand side), perhaps to be filled by a second municipal position, such as *Iivir* (*duumvir*, the chief civic magistracy in a *municipium*).

Line 5: the phrase can most likely be restored in full as *decreto decurionum pecunia publica* but, on the assumption that only *perpetuo* stood in line 4, the likely extent of the missing portion of the inscription on the left means that the first two words were probably abbreviated to the standard *D(ecreto) D(ecurionum)*.

The text cannot be closely dated, but is likely to be Augustan or Julio-Claudian.

The text bears close similarities (letter forms and material) to ISic3574 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3574>] (for *Alfia*), but that text is thicker, the line heights are different, the guidelines are much more pronounced, and it is not possible to see how the two texts could be combined. They must be regarded as separate, but presumably contemporary, inscriptions.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645642

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. *Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.16

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-09): ISic3571. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021559>

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